

Tourism Reforms and the Creation of Prospective Projects Based on Modern Principles (Case Study of Samarkand Region)

Gulmira Keldiyarova,

Iroda Abulfayziyeva

Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

Khusanova Mamura Sheralievna

Lecturer at the Abu Ali Ibn Sina College of Public Health, Kattakurgan

Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Sep 2024; **Published:** 14 Oct 2024

Abstract: This article examines the present condition of tourism destinations in our country, the developments being implemented, and the ongoing reforms. Additionally, it examines the challenges associated with tourism growth in areas of natural beauty through the implementation of contemporary projects.

Key words: *tourism reforms, sustainable tourism development, national parks of Uzbekistan, ecotourism destinations, biodiversity conservation, environmental protection.*

Introduction: Tourism is a multifaceted domain with substantial economic and socio-cultural importance. It is ranked third globally in profitability. Another significant characteristic is its capacity to generate multiple employment opportunities with minimum expenditure. Hotels are a crucial component of tourism. Our nation is implementing comprehensive strategies to enhance tourism. The nation's government is focusing on incentivizing tourist entrepreneurs, luring foreign consulting firms, elevating hotel standards to international levels, and growing the number of hotels that comply with global norms. An explicit illustration of this is the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan of January 5, 2019, titled "On measures to accelerate the development of the tourism industry."

National parks are designated areas of remarkable ecological, cultural, and aesthetic significance, safeguarded for conservation, recreation, research, and cultural activities. National parks are created as state nature conservation entities through decisions made by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan or local authorities, after recommendations from pertinent state agencies, and are categorised into national parks of national and local significance.

Ecotourism Destinations: Ecotourism destinations like "Boboyong'oq,"

“O’riklisoy,” “Sharshara,” “Sherbuloq,” and “Ming yoshli archa” in the O’riklisoy area, and “Miq qal’asi” in the Yettikechuvsoy area, are already established. Additionally, 456 hectares of land in the Zomin National Park have been allocated to the “Suffa 2400” tourism directorate.

National parks are designated regions of exceptional ecological, cultural, and aesthetic importance, preserved for conservation, recreation, research, and cultural pursuits. They are established as state nature conservation entities through resolutions by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan or local authorities, following recommendations from relevant state agencies, and are classified into national parks of national and local significance..

Distance to Dashtobod railway station: 70 km

Distance to Jizzakh city: 110 km

Distance to Samarkand: 310 km

Methods: The methods used for ecological research are primarily:

Descriptive method:

Comparative method:

Experimental method:

Modeling method: The first three methods are similar to those used in biological sciences. Experimentation and modeling are widely used in ecology.

Environmental research methods: All methods used for environmental research can be divided into three major categories:

Field method: The field method is employed to examine the synergistic effects of environmental factors on populations in their natural habitats. This approach facilitates the investigation of biosystem development and their vital activities, as well as the environmental influences upon them. Meteorological observations and population assessments are conducted utilising the field method. Data from observations, notes, photographs, and videos are meticulously documented.

Ecological experimental method: This strategy is employed to examine the influence of specific elements on organismal growth. Studying the impact of a specific element on an organism or community in isolation within a natural context is unfeasible, as all factors interact in a complicated manner. A particular natural system is typically modelled to attain this objective. An aquarium can be regarded as a representation of a freshwater basin.

Mathematical modeling method: This approach aids in forecasting the stability and future of an ecosystem. Computers are extensively utilized in this approach. The approach entails transforming the characteristics of the system under examination into mathematical formulations. Subsequently, by altering the values of specific indicators, the modifications occurring inside the examined system are analysed. These ecological models are constructed using extensive data gathered from both natural and laboratory environments. These mathematical models facilitate the examination of scenarios that are challenging to test empirically. They facilitate the forecasting of ecosystem evolution in response to climate change and anthropogenic influences. Research methodologies employed in ecology are frequently utilised in conjunction to examine the environment.

Analysis and Evaluation: The number of tourists coming to Uzbekistan annually is growing: in 2005, the number of tourists visiting Uzbekistan amounted to 240 thousand people from 117 countries of the world, and in 2017, more than 2.5 million tourists visited Uzbekistan.

The number of tourists in 2018 amounted to 5.3 million, including 5 million from the CIS countries, 325 thousand from abroad. An international tourism fair is held in Uzbekistan every autumn. The share of tourists who entered the Republic of Uzbekistan for the purpose of tourism in 2006 and 2007 is 9% of the total number of arrivals. In 2007, 27,264 more people entered Uzbekistan for tourism than in 2006 (66% more). 80% of those who entered are citizens of the CIS (726,669 people), and 20% are citizens of other foreign countries.

The share of tourists entering for the purpose of tourism in the context of states is different-72% of tourists are citizens of foreign countries, and 28% are citizens of CIS countries. According to the statistical Internet survey conducted from May 7 to August 7, 2008, the majority of respondents - 39% - visit the country because of their interest in its historical and architectural attractions. Another group — 24% - visits Uzbekistan to get acquainted with culture, traditions and lifestyle.

Thus, most tourists wish to visit: historical sites, monuments, museums and art galleries, ancient buildings and structures (for example, ancient fortresses, mosques, madrasas, libraries, former prisons and wells), as well as parks, national festivals and other cultural events. The office of the World Tourism Organization (WTO) was opened in Samarkand in 2004. This office is designed to coordinate the efforts of international organizations and national tourism organizations of the countries located on the Great Silk Road.

According to the US Department of State, Uzbekistan is in the group of safe countries for tourism, in which the usual precautions should be taken.

Our region features natural wonders and extensive ecotourism locations that provide distinctive experiences for visitors. The recently constructed Omonqo'ton National Park is currently attracting visitors.

Omonqo'ton National Park: The park encompasses 1500 hectares and is situated at an elevation of 1600-1800 meters above sea level. The region comprises 1000 hectares of reserve zone, 400 ha of recreational zone, and 100 hectares of economic zone. The park is situated in the Urgut district of the Samarkand area, within the Zarafshon mountain ranges, notably on the eastern flank of the Taxti Qoracha pass (M-39 highway). The park's main area include forests, mountains, and other natural sceneries.

Flora: Omonqo'ton National Park features over 1300 plant species, encompassing more than 60 medicinal varieties, including deerweed, mountain basil, mountain mint, agrimony, St. John's Wort, immortelle, mugwort, wild carrot, plantain, mountain onion, mountain tea, cumin, barberry, ginger, four species of wild plums, wild pear, wild raspberry, among others. The primary trees and plants comprise acacia, ailanthus, bitter almond, Crimean pine, Zarafshon juniper, oak, ash, pistachio, walnut, maple, white raspberry, plum, apple, elm, hawthorn, buckthorn, among others. Additionally, there exist mountain tulips (*Tulipa korolkowii*), saffron flowers

(Iris), pyramid flowers, cornflowers, chicory (both white and yellow types), wild lilies, chamomile, and numerous other floral species.

Fauna: 127 species of vertebrates have been identified, including 11 species of mammals (wolf, fox, jackal, hare, badger, hedgehog, marten, etc.).

Image 1: Current state of Omonqo'ton National Park.

Omonqo'ton National Park is one of the most important sites for protecting nature, preserving biodiversity, and conserving flora and fauna. Protecting nature and treating it responsibly is the human duty of each of us.

Conclusion: The creation of Omonqo'ton National Park, which provides novel attractions and experiences, is essential for its development into a tourism destination grounded on contemporary initiatives and unique concepts. The establishment of Omonqo'ton will generate employment opportunities for several local residents, promote a reasonable relationship with nature, and cultivate ecological awareness. Numerous guesthouses, tea rooms, and restaurants exist in the settlements adjacent to the national park. Nonetheless, human activities are causing pollution in the park. The national park's terrain has deteriorated and is in a lamentable condition due to visitor activity.

References

1. Ubaidullaev S. et al. Tourism in Uzbekistan //Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance. - 2021. - Vol. 2. - No. 4. - pp. 6-10.
2. Ruzieva D. I., Gafarova D. T. Ways of development and popularization of cultural tourism in Uzbekistan // WIRTSCHAFT UND MANAGEMENT: THEORIE UND PRAXIS. - 2014. - pp. 99-102.
3. Solieva G. A., Dedazhanov B. N., Karimzhanova R. M. Tourism in Uzbekistan and the role of marketing in its development //A young scientist. - 2020. - No. 5. - pp. 132-134.
4. Dzhumanova A. B., Kushakova M. N. THE ROLE OF UZBEKISTAN TEMIR YULLARI JSC IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN //Economics and society. - 2018. - №. 10

- (53). - Pp. 249-252.
5. Farmanov E. A., Kadyrov D. H., Khodjaeva F. N. The role of Uzbekistan's cultural heritage in the development of tourism //Bulletin of Science and Education. - 2020. - No. 2-3 (80). - pp. 20-23.
 6. Urolova D. B., Tolipov M. U. U. Factors influencing the development of tourism in Uzbekistan //Achievements of science and education. - 2020. - №. 3 (57). - Pp. 21-23.
 7. Akhmedov J. D., Abdurashidova J. F. The development of extreme tourism in Uzbekistan //Universum: economics and jurisprudence. - 2021. - №. 12 (87). - Pp. 4-7.
 8. Akhmedov J. D., Abdurashidova J. F. The development of extreme tourism in Uzbekistan //Universum: economics and jurisprudence. - 2021. - №. 12 (87). - Pp. 4-7.
 9. Reimbayeva G. Civil law regulation of the contract for the provision of tourist services //Science and technology in the modern world. - 2023. - vol. 2. -No. 10. - pp. 43-44.
 10. Dzhuraeva N. B. Review of health tourism in the context of the tourism strategy of Uzbekistan //Education is science and innovative ideas in the world. - 2023. - vol. 16. - No. 4. - pp. 13-17.
 11. Rakhimova D. Actual directions of development of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan //Engineering problems and innovations. - 2023.